

3D printing of a multi-performative building envelope: Assessment of air permeability, water tightness, wind loads, and impact resistance

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the 3D printing feasibility of mono-material facade panels with recycled thermoplastic. The design had integrated performance parameters, namely air permeability, water tightness, resistance to wind loads, and impact resistance, and fabrication parameters in a computational iterative process to inform the geometry topology. The fabrication parameters were integrated and evaluated for geometry accuracy, print path accuracy of 5 mm length, overhang higher than 45°, inner layer adhesion, and adhesion to the print bed. Two panels, measuring 1.6-m length and 2-m height, and six connections were fabricated and evaluated in a standardized facade testing rig. The air permeability displayed a larger than 1.5 m³/m²·h permissible Class 1 value due to air gaps in the manufactured panels. The same gaps that occurred during the fabrication process permitted water flow in both panels after 7 min of testing. The panels passed standardized serviceability and safety standards for wind load resistance and achieved a maximum E5 class for impact resistance. The structural strength values were 1500 Pa for serviceability, 2250 Pa for safety load, and 3262 Pa for breaking load. These findings demonstrated that 3D-printed geometries have a high potential to facilitate sustainable design strategies by integrating multiple performances within a mono-material building envelope.

1. Introduction

3D printing (3DP) or additive manufacturing (AM) is an emerging technique in the architectural field, due to its versatility and customized solutions. This method offers a high potential for building facades, allowing for free-form designs [1]. 3DP facade panels can be durable yet lightweight, making them ideal for prefabricated solutions with easy and fast installation, and reduced structural loads [2].

The material plays an essential role in the AM process, as it has the potential to enable the production of complex facade elements with a single material. Such a mono-material element could be more easily recycled at the end of its life cycle compared to multi-layered solutions. Depending on its intended purpose, this mono-material element can be fabricated using thermoplastics, clay-

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based materials, concrete, or metal [3]. Nevertheless, to this date, thermoplastic is considered the most suitable for a mono-material complex geometry fabrication. This is because, it has the potential to enable higher design freedom and building rate while also providing transparency, good thermal resistance, low density (lightweight), and recyclable material properties [4].

AM has different processes to manufacture thermoplastic polymers, with the most notable known as VAT photo-polymerization, material jetting, binder jetting, powder bed fusion, sheet lamination, directed energy deposition, and material extrusion [5]. Currently, material extrusion is the most promising AM technique for fabricating large-scale prototypes, with a high potential for architectural applications [6,7]. At the present moment, the majority of 3DP facades have been built with an ornamental purpose. However, this technology allows to go beyond the novel aesthetic illustrated in most up-to-date projects. For example, TU Delft researchers built in 2017 "SPONG3D", displaying a 3DP adaptive facade panel that integrates environmental performances in a mono-material geometry. SPONG3D proved the potential of integrating active temperature control in AM building components [8]. This study also highlighted that further investigation is required to add additional performances to the design process. In 2023 Piccioni et al., demonstrated that thermal transmittance of 3DP thermoplastic elements can be suitable for various climate conditions, ranging from 1 to 1.7 W/m²K only by changing the internal cavity distribution and size [9]. In 2017, Studio Roland Snooks displayed a large-scale thermoplastic wall for indoor applications with the "RMIT School of Design" project. This interior facade passed indoor fire and building regulations for Australia [10]. Moreover, in the past five years several studies showcased that building an energy-efficient designs can be achieved with daylight transmission and distribution tailored in the 3DP facade scale, cardinal orientation, and location in the world [11–14].

These studies demonstrated the potential of monolithic prefabricated facade solutions. However, they primarily address a single performance, since overcoming fabrication challenges was a necessary first step. In 2019, Mungenast proved the potential of considering multiple functionalities in a 3DP facade panel, such as fire resistance, insulation, load transfer, and shading [15]. Computational-based tools were used to design the facade panels and conduct experimental testing to verify their structural strength, fire resistance, and thermal performance. It is noteworthy that these multiple performance aspects were evaluated post-fabrication, with the primary focus on assessing the feasibility of 3DP for facade applications. The computational design identified biomimetic concepts and fabrication constraints. Although environmental considerations were not incorporated into the geometric design, the thesis successfully demonstrated the potential of additive manufacturing for multi-functional 3DP facades, highlighting applications that extend beyond purely ornamental aesthetics.

By examining the highlighted projects, a noticeable trend is visible within the field of 3DP facades, which emphasizes the fabrication potential and integration of environmental performance. Yet, facade components need to address holistically multiple parameters to ensure indoor comfort, security against outdoor weathering, and suitability for real-world building applications [16]. In addition to thermal and daylight performances, considerations such as assembly, air permeability, water tightness, and structural strength against wind loads and impacts are crucial to be integrated. These environmental performance criteria, along with 3DP parameters, need to be seamlessly consolidated to achieve sustainable solutions [17,18].

To date, the successful integration of multiple environmental parameters into the computational design process has yet to be fully demonstrated. This challenge persists due to the complexity involved in designing and manufacturing a monolithic building envelope, which requires the careful coordination of numerous fabrication and environmental factors. The intricate computational demands of integrating these parameters to ensure the successful realization of a fabricated geometry remain a significant barrier. In addressing the fabrication challenges, such as print path length and width accuracy, print temperatures and environment, adhesion to the print bed, and inner-layer adhesion can potentially ensure the quality of AM prototypes [19].

Therefore, this study examines the multi-performative feasibility of a 3DP facade with a mono-material. The computational design process is integrative, informed by both fabrication and environmental parameters. The readiness of the 3DP facade for building applications is evaluated through its performance in assembly solutions, air permeability, water tightness, resistance to wind loads, and impact resistance. The novelty of this approach lies in integrating multiple performances within the computational design, which directly informs the geometry and topology of the facade. Another significant novelty is in building a facade-systems that incorporates connections and integrated brackets within prefabricated panels made from a single monolithic recycled thermoplastic. This prototype is tested and validated using a real-world facade test rig to analyze its performance and demonstrate the potential for passive, automated building elements in architectural applications.

Fig. 1. Methodology of the 3DP facade, with computational design is informed by environmental and fabrication parameters.

2. Materials and methods

The methodology of this study relies on a heuristic technique to validate the fabrication and environmental performance results. The study was carried out in three experimental steps and are detailed as follows.

1. Computational design - a facade design process that integrates iteratively fabrication parameters and environmental performances, see Fig. 1
2. Fabrication experiments in a 3DP setup.
3. Environmental performance experiments in a facade testing rig.

2.1. Computational design

The computational design process of the facade is iterative to facilitate the seamless integration of multiple parameters, see Fig. 2. These parameters are.

- Fabrication parameters, such as geometry accuracy, print path accuracy overhang, inner layer adhesion, and adhesion to the print bed.
- Environmental performances, namely air permeability, water tightness, resistance to wind loads, and impact resistance.

The facade design is comprised of two panels and eight connections, with a total boundary dimension of 1600 mm × 150 mm × 2000 mm, see Fig. 3a. The connections are designed and fabricated separately from the panels due to their inherent geometric complexity. This approach proved to have a significantly lower risk of geometric failure when the connections were tested separately during the fabrication phase. This is because their design process is highly complex and different for each individual part, see 2.1.2 Connections.

2.1.1. Facade panels

The two panels are designed for the city of Zurich, Switzerland. Their main constituent parts are (1) Front surface, (2) Infill, and (3) Back surface with integrated brackets, see Fig. 3b.

First, the front surface (1) of the facade panels is exposed to the outdoor environment which makes it susceptible to sudden dynamic loads. For this reason, the front geometry considers the impact resistance parameter. This geometry consists of a zigzag pattern, which has proven suitable impact-resisting properties in smaller-scale 3DP components [20]. Additionally, several large-scale fabrication tests of this pattern demonstrated that an opening range of the diagonal measuring 50 mm–200 mm and overhang angle higher than 45° can prevent deformation of thermoplastic panels [14]. These fabrication parameters were considered in tandem with the environmental performance when designing the topology optimization of the front surface zigzag pattern, see Fig. 4a. The pattern was built with non-uniform rational basis splines (NURBS) in Grasshopper, a Rhinoceros plug-in [21]. Then, these NURBS were extruded into boundary representation (BREP) surfaces.

Second, the infill (2) was designed as a continuation of the front surface zigzag pattern with the overhang respecting a higher than 45° angle. The infill incorporated wind load resistance through two fabrication criteria: the printing direction and functional gradient [22]. The printing direction of the panels is perpendicular to the wind loads which secures a better structural strength (calculations in supplementary material) [23,24]. The topology optimization considered a gradient distribution optimized by allocating more material to the critical section of the panel, the bracket area and connections, and removing the material from the middle section of the facade panels, see Fig. 4b. This gradient distribution is denser for the connection and the bracket area of 50 mm distance, and less dense for the

Fig. 2. Computational design process of the facade panels and connections.

Fig. 3. a) Isometric view of the facade element comprised of two panels and exploded isometric view of the two panels and their respective connections: Horizontal connections (HcA and HcB), Vertical connections (VcA and VcB); b) Isometric view of the facade panel consisting of the (1) Front surface, (2) Infill, and (3) Back surface with brackets.

middle section of 200 mm distance. The middle section of the facade panels is not as structurally critical compared to the connection and bracket area. The connections and brackets are more susceptible to concentrated loads and stress and require a higher structural strength. Therefore, the infill design is optimized to use only the necessary amount of material in the critical section, reducing fabrication time and sample weight.

Third, the back surface (3) of the facade panel is exposed to the indoor space and plays an essential role in connecting to the building structure. This surface is modeled with NURBS and then constructed as a BREP (Fig. 4c). On the upper side of the back surface, two brackets were added to secure coupling to the building structure, see Fig. 5.

The most essential fabrication parameters considered for the brackets design are overhang, print path width, and height. The overhang angle is designed 45° for the lower side of the bracket, while the print path and width are both 2 mm to secure adhesion of the bracket layers. The printing direction is perpendicular to the loads applied on the facade brackets, as this orientation has been shown to offer greater load resistance [24]. The structural dimension of the brackets has been calculated based on the theory of elasticity of materials. Different specimens of the material were tested to confirm the calculated values. In these calculations, a conservative 15 MPa yield strength was used, although the material had an anisotropic behavior. This value is estimated from initial individual tests on the brackets, to ensure that load transmission is adequate in the facade element (Section 2 in supplementary material) [24]. With this assumption, a 10 mm wall rectangular section has been checked in a conservative estimation as a solid piece. It was concluded that for a panel 1.8 m wide and 3.5 m high, the material works at 78 % of its use for a 1.5 kPa design wind load. This wind load was estimated based on calculations for a facade in a Zurich building measuring 15 m × 20 m × 40 m, in accordance with the SIA 261 standard [25].

Fig. 4. a) Zigzag pattern of the front surface (1) with opening range of 50–200 mm in the above picture, and NURB curves of the back surface in the picture below; b) Infill gradient section displayed at a 70 mm height (1), 250 mm height (2), and 400 mm height (3) with opening range between 50 and 200 mm.

Fig. 5. Two brackets are attached to the back surface upper side, which has a 45° overhang angle and perpendicular printing direction to the wind loads.

Finally, the front surface (1), infill (2), and back surface with brackets (3) were all joined together in a single BREP. The distances between the BREP surfaces were designed to be smaller than 2 mm for securing layer adhesion between the front surface, infill, and back surface. The joined BREP was sliced into a ready-for-fabrication 3DP tool path at 2 mm layer height and 5–6 mm layer width. Then, a series of couplings were integrated into the first two layers of the design at a 100 mm distance to secure adhesion to the print bed and prevent high deformations of the panel. Following, a custom module developed in Python stored the sliced tool path data into XYZ coordinates, extrusion values, fabrication speed, layer index number, and print path width. This data was saved by the Python module into a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) file [26]. Further, COMPAS RRC was used to run the JSON file by securing an online communication of instructions for the ABB Robots [27].

2.1.2. Connections

To cope with the manufacturing tolerances of the panel, bespoke connections were designed and fabricated independently from the panels. These connections, namely Horizontal connection A (HcA), Horizontal connection B (HcB), Vertical connection A (VcA), and Vertical connection B (VcB) integrated air permeability, water tightness, and resistance to wind loads in the computational design. Their geometric configuration was adapted from established conventional solutions, such as aluminum joints. The connections configuration had one water gasket placed towards the front surface (or outdoor space) to protect against water ingress (F), and two air gaskets towards the back surface (or indoor space) to prevent air infiltration (H), see Fig. 6. The key difference between horizontal and vertical connections is the added fastener (I) in the horizontal section. This fastener ensures a tight fit with the facade panel and prevents any loosening of the HcA and HcB during wind loads. All prototypes were modeled with NURBS with an overhang higher than 50° angle. In this process, was highly essential to have an accurate geometry and secure precise alignment and assembly between parts. An overhang higher than 50° had higher chances to prevent any fabrication failures. The overall geometry was designed with the printing direction parallel to the sample's length and perpendicular to the wind loads. Consequently, the structural insert area (G) has a perpendicular printing direction. This orientation helps to prevent delamination between layers under wind loads, as a perpendicular printing direction to the applied force ensures better structural performance. The designed NURBS were extruded into BREPs to create

Fig. 6. Horizontal and vertical connections: (A) Facade panel 1, (B) Facade panel 2, (C) Horizontal Connection B - HcB, (D) Horizontal Connection A - HcA, (E) Silicone filled gaps, (F) Water tightness gasket, (G) Structural insert, (H) Two air gaskets for air permeability, (I) Fastener.

Fig. 7. a) Off-the-shelf gaskets for water tightness and air permeability; b) PIPG thermoplastic pellets; c) ABB IRB 4600 Robotic Arm attached to a gantry; d) E25 thermo-plastic pellet extruder.

a 3D volume representation of the design. Then, the BREP was sliced into a ready-for-fabrication 3DP path of 5–6 mm width and 2 mm height.

2.2. Fabrication setup

In this study, iterative 3DP tests were conducted to fabricate the computational geometry. The 3DP tests setup was comprised of an IRB 4600 Robotic Arm attached to a gantry in the Robotic Fabrication Laboratory at ETH Zurich, which had a large-scale E25 pellet extruder as its end effector, see Fig. 7c [28,29]. The E25 pellet extruder had a 12 kg/h thermoplastic extrusion output, which can work with robotic speeds reaching up to 250 mm/s, see Fig. 7d. It contained four heating zones with customized temperature control, T1, T2, T3, and T4 as the nozzle. All samples were printed with a 4 mm nozzle diameter on a non-heated printing bed, dimensions of 2500 × 2500 mm. The printing bed consisted of medium-density fiberboard (MDF) plates mounted to a supporting frame of aluminum profiles. The material used for 3DP the facade element and connections was post-industrial polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PIPG). PIPG was comprised of 30 % glass fiber and 70 % post-industrial polyethylene terephthalate glycol recycled from industrial processes, see Fig. 7b. Recycled thermoplastic pellets, such as PETG, PP, and PC have been previously tested for large-scale experiments. However, compared to the other thermoplastics, PIPG has been proven as a more reliable 3DP material [30]. PIPG, due to its high glass fiber content, prevents deformations of the overall geometry in large-scale 3DP components, has a lower print line expansion, smooth print line, form stability of the print line, good adhesion to the print bed, and inner layer adhesion [19]. Before fabrication tests, the material was dried for 4 hours at 60° Celsius with a VisMec Dryplus 50 [31].

For the connections, an elastic material was required for the air and water barriers. Given the experimental nature of the prototypes, the authors decided that off-the-shelf conventional gaskets were more likely to prevent water and air infiltration. The automated fabrication of these gaskets was outside the scope of this study. The gaskets were purchased from Jansen AG Schüco with reference numbers illustrated in Table 1. They are made from ethylene propylene diene terpolymer (EPDM), and are market available and consolidated elements, see Fig. 7a. The gaps between the facade panels and connections were filled with off-the-shelf silicone sealing (see E in Fig. 6).

The main fabrication parameters considered for analyzing the fabrication results are.

- Geometry accuracy - the overall fabricated shape is validated if it has similar dimensions to the simulated model without any visible deformations to the naked eye.
- Print path accuracy - the fabricated print layer is validated if it has a similar position, dimensions, and smoothness to the simulated model tool path.
- Overhang - the fabricated geometry has no protuberance, where the material extends outwards or inwards its designed shape due to a low printing angle.
- Inner layer adhesion - no delamination occurs in the print path.
- Adhesion to print bed - the position of the prototype remains stable on the print bed during and after fabrication.

The fabrication settings, for both the facade panel and connections, such as robotic speed, material extrusion values, or temperatures, were adjusted in the experimental testing until an accurate outcome was concluded, see Tables 2 and 3.

2.3. Facade test rig setup

The environmental performance testing was based on the SN EN 13830:2003 standard. A facade rig setup was used to measure air permeability, water tightness, wind loads, and impact resistance values. This setup is a test chamber of 2000 × 2500 mm opening, customized to fit the 3DP facade dimensions of 1600 × 2000 mm with oriented strand board (OSB) panels, see Fig. 8. The measuring equipment was calibrated every two years according to the specifications of ISO 17025:2018 "General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories". The facade element testing was carried out according to SN EN 13830:2003 in the following sequence.

1. Facade panels assembly and fastening to structure,
2. Air permeability - for classification according to SN EN 12153:2000,
3. Water tightness test static - for classification according to SN EN 12155:2000,

Table 1

Air permeability and water tightness gasket names and reference number.

Front chamber gasket 15 B 245,180	Coupling gasket 245,168	Coupling gasket (Stack joint) 246,504	Front chamber gasket corner 15/15 BB 245,090

Table 2

Fabrication settings of the facade panels (*rpm = rotation per minute).

No	Fabrication settings	Panel 1	Panel 2
1	Material	PIPG	PIPG
2	Ambient temperature	19 °C	14 °C
3	Average print path length/layer	17.90 m	17.26
4	Layer height	2 mm	2 mm
5	Layer width	5 ± 1 mm	5 ± 1 mm
6	Overhang angle	45°	45°
7	Nozzle diameter	4 mm	4 mm
8	Extruder temperatures T1, T2, T3, T4	235, 260, 270, 275 °C	235, 270, 280, 285 °C
9	Robot speed	100 mm/s	100 mm/s
10	Extrusion values	48 rpm*	48 rpm*
11	Sample height	840 mm	840 mm
12	Cooling + heated bed	no	no
13	Weight	119 kg	112 kg
14	Fabrication time	20 h 56 min	20 h 10 min

Table 3

Fabrication settings of the facade connections: two horizontal connections A (2HcA), two horizontal connections B (2HcB), vertical connection A (VcA), and vertical connection B (VcB). *rpm = rotation per minute.

No	Fabrication settings	2 × HcA	2 × HcB	VcA	VcB
1	Material	PIPG	PIPG	PIPG	PIPG
2	Ambient temperature	19 °C	19 °C	19 °C	19 °C
3	Average print path length/layer	6.90 m	7.21 m	21.88 m	28.89 m
4	Layer height	2 mm	2 mm	2 mm	2 mm
5	Layer width	5 ± 1 mm			
6	Overhang angle	50°	50°	50°	50°
7	Nozzle diameter	4 mm	4 mm	4 mm	4 mm
8	Extruder temperatures T1, T2, T3, T4	235, 255, 265, 275 °C			
9	Robot speed	50 mm/s	70 mm/s	140 mm/s	80 mm/s
10	Extrusion values	15 rpm*	17 rpm*	35 rpm*	15 rpm*
11	Sample height	106 mm	86 mm	100 mm	60 mm
12	Cooling + heated bed	no	no	no	no
13	Weight	7 kg	6 kg	14 kg	12 kg
14	Fabrication time	1 h 55 min	1 h 35 min	3 h 40 min	3 h 10 min

4. Resistance to wind load - serviceability according to SN EN 12179:2000,
5. Air permeability - for confirmation the classification according to SN EN 12153:2000,
6. Water tightness test static - to confirm the classification according to SN EN 12155:2000,
7. Resistance to wind load, safety test according to SN EN 12179:2000,
8. Impact test according to SN EN 14019:2016,
9. Resistance to wind load, breaking load,
10. Facade panels dismantling.

2.3.1. Air permeability

Air permeability was tested with centrifugal fans and the associated piping and control valves which provides air supply to the test chamber. The direction of the volume flow can be switched by changeover flaps to create positive and negative test pressures. This control system provided a constant test pressure with a constant volume flow for testing the air permeability, as well as water tightness and resistance to wind load of the facade element. One transducer, the TA10 165 GE Höntsch AG, with a 20–600 m³/h range, was used to measure the volume flow rate with a maximum deviation limit of 5 % from the analyzed value. The measurement of air permeability through all fixed elements q_A (m³/h·m²) for classification was:

$$q_A = Q/A = (Q_1 - Q_0)/A$$

The measurement of air permeability through closed connections q_L (m³/h·m) for classification was:

$$q_L = Q/L = (Q_1 - Q_0)/L$$

Q₀ is the test chamber leakage and Q₁ is the air flow through the test chamber and the test facade. A is the total specimen area of 3.3 m², and L is the connection length of 9.3 m. The maximum values for air permeability at 150 Pa pressure difference for Class 1, according to the SN EN 12152:2002 standard, are less than 1.5 m³/(h·m²) for q_A and less than 0.5 m³/(h·m) for q_L. The q_n (m³/h·m²) air permeability values were calculated according to:

Fig. 8. Facade test rig chamber. Metal brackets (visible in the picture on the right) are assembled on a wooden beam to connect to the 3DP facade brackets.

$$q_n = q_0(p_n / p_0)^{2/3}$$

In this equation, p_n is the positive intermediate test pressure, and q_0 is the permissible air permeability at positive maximum test pressure p_0 . These experimental assessments were based on the SN EN 12153 test for the SN EN 12152 classification.

2.3.2. Water tightness

Water tightness experiments testing had a water spray system consisting of 2 bars with 400 mm spacing spray nozzles. The nozzles provide 120° cone-shaped water distribution and are placed 250 mm from the facade panels. The water amount was uniformly distributed through the two rows of spray nozzles at 50 % each (3.3 l/min) on the front surface of the facade element in a constant water film. This water flow was adjusted and measured by control valves, the EP020R + MP Belimo, of 6–40 l/min measuring range, at a maximum 10 % deviation limit from the measured value. Three positive pressure pulses of 660 Pa were applied before the test, where each pressure pulse was held for minimum 3 seconds. At the beginning of the test, the facade element was completely sprayed with water for 15 min without test pressure. Then sequential test pressures of 50, 100, 150, 200, 300, 450 and 600 Pa were incrementally applied for 5 minutes. Afterwards, the test pressure was returned to zero and the water spraying was stopped. The required water amount was calculated based on the facade element area multiplied by 2 l/(min·m²). Thus, the total amount of required water was:

$$T_{water} = 3.3m^2 \cdot 2l/min \cdot m^2 = 6.6l/min$$

These static water tightness experiments were based on the SN EN 12155 test and SN EN 12154 classification.

2.3.3. Resistance to wind loads

Resistance to wind loads for positive and negative testing pressure was carried out in three experimental steps to identify: i) serviceability, ii) safety load, and iii) breaking load. The serviceability (i) and safety load (ii) were based on the SN EN 12179 standard test and SN EN 13116 classification. The test values were measured by 3 differential pressure sensors with a maximum deviation limit of 5 %, the IDP 100 ICS Schneider Messtechnik, with a measuring range of ±1000 Pa for sensor 1, ±5000 Pa for sensor 2, and ±10000 Pa for sensor 3. These 3 sensors were placed in the test chamber and connected via separate hoses so that the static pressure is determined independently from the air supply. The test procedure started with three pressure pulses of 50 % from the ± 1.5 kPa value derived from calculations (Section 4 in supplementary material) [24]. After these pulses, the deformation sensors were set to zero and the wind load were applied in incremental steps of 25 %. The pressure levels of wind load serviceability for negative loads (wind suction) and positive loads (wind pressure) were.

- Negative three pulses of 750 Pa at 375, 750, 1125, and 1500 Pa
- Positive three pulses of -750 Pa at -375, -750, -1125, and -1500 Pa

The 3 deflection sensors of 0.1 mm accuracy, Burster 8712-50, Burster 8712-100, and Burster 8712-150 were used to measure the facade deformation under the negative and positive pulses. All three sensors were placed inside the test chamber, with S_{middle} as the 2nd sensor placed in the middle of the panel height. S_{up} was the 1st sensor placed in the upper side of the panel and S_{down} as the 3rd

sensor placed in the lower side of the facade panel. The measured values of these sensors helped to calculate the relative frontal deflections (W) of the facade elements as follows:

$$W = S_{\text{middle}} - [(S_{\text{up}} + S_{\text{down}})]/2$$

According to SN EN 13116:2001, The maximum value for W must not be greater than $L/200$ or 15 mm, where L was the measured distance between structural points of the frame element. Additionally, the deflection must be also temporary and deform back by at least 95 % up to a maximum of 1 hour after the load removal. After the serviceability (i), air permeability, and water tightness tests a safety load (ii) of 2500 Pa and -2500 Pa was applied. Then after the impact test, a breaking load (iii) was applied with increasing pressure until the facade element broke or the maximum power of the fan was reached.

2.3.4. Impact resistance

Impact resistance was tested according to the SN EN 14019:2016 standard and classification. The test was comprised of several drop heights of the same 50 kg weight incrementally applied from the smallest distance of 200 mm to the maximum values of 300 mm, 450 mm, 700 mm, and 950 mm respectively. Three targets were selected on the facade element as the most critical points for impact testing, the two panels center, and vertical connection, see Fig. 9.

3. Results and discussion

This section details the results of integrating fabrication and environmental performance in the computational design to secure a multi-performative 3DP facade element. The fabrication results were evaluated by fabrication parameters regarding geometry accuracy, print path accuracy, overhang, inner layer adhesion, and adhesion to the print bed of the facade panels and connections. The environmental performances were evaluated for air permeability, water tightness, resistance to wind loads, and impact resistance, as well as facade panel assembly and dismantling.

3.1. Fabrication

Two panels and six connections were fabricated with PIPG. No delamination or cracks were visible in the overall prototype. The front surface proved accurate for the overall geometry, see Fig. 10a. However, several visible gaps occurred in the facade panels and connections, see Fig. 10b. These gaps are more visible in the areas with double curvature or less than 60° overhang. Additionally, in the experimental process the higher the robotic speed, from 100 mm/s to 120 mm/s the more limited was the material extrusion output

Fig. 9. Three impact points for the impact resistance tests.

with a maximum permissible 48 rotations per minute (rpm). The authors estimate that the cause of these hardware limitations are the long working continuous hours, 20 hours, for the extruder server motor, which tends to overheat. Although a higher fabrication speed decreased the manufacturing time, the 100 mm/s speed also limited the extrusion output. The designed print path width of 5–6 mm diminished to 3–4 mm. This 3–4 mm width contributed to overhangs and poor inner layer adhesion in critical areas of the double curvature of the geometry. In contrast, material protruded in the corner areas, where the acceleration of the robot arm usually decreased during fabrication. Visible intersection occurred between the infill and front surface which produced minor fabrication errors, see Fig. 10c. At the same time, the infill did not connect in some areas with the front and back surface of the gradient, which could bring a risk of the structural strength of the panel, see Fig. 10d. Nevertheless, the couplings integrated in the first layers of the tool path supported a good print bed adhesion, which prevented the deformations in the overall geometry, see Fig. 10e. The authors believe that additional fabrication testing, where the overhang is increased from 45° to 65° degrees and an increased material extrusion output from 48 rpm to 56–58 rpm could contribute to more accurate geometries. Additionally, several modifications in the digital geometry, for example a higher distance than 2 mm in the corner areas could potentially reduce some of the inaccuracies. Nevertheless, such errors are only detectable after several fabrication tests. They are highly correlated to the fabrication parameters than require to be adjusted during the experimental process. For this reason, it is strongly recommended to use an iterative experimental process to correct the digital model and secure accurate results.

The infill gradient fabrication had an overall good geometry quality. This gradient proved successful in transition from smaller (50 mm) to larger gaps (100 mm), see Fig. 11a. The brackets were also successfully integrated in the back surface. The width between the bracket layers is smaller than 2 mm, which generated material overflow. In the case of the brackets, material overflow was recommended to secure a tighter adhesion between layers and provide a better structural strength.

For the facade connections, the fabrication process of HcA and HcB required additional support. These horizontal connections had a fastener (I), compared to the vertical ones which required a wooden support. This support was easily removed after the printing process. The prototypes were fabricated in several iterative tests, which demonstrated high dimensional accuracy, allowing for smooth and precise interlocking between connection A and B, see Fig. 11b. The interlocking provided a stable and reliable connection between the HcA and HcB, and the VcA and VcB parts. However, gaps occurred in all connections due to varied print width of the layers. The gaps occurred at the infill of the connections. Although the distance was 3 mm, due to uneven acceleration of the robot the corner areas were overflowed with material, while middle section had a smaller print path width. An optimized gradient, dependent on the robotic acceleration with 3 mm print path at the corners and 2 mm in the middle sections could secure a better accuracy. Nevertheless, these fabrication errors could lead to further air and water infiltration.

3.2. Assembly and dismantling

An initial test for the facade assembly was performed to identify the facade and connection installation ability in the test rig. The assembly of the connections with the facade panels was relatively effortless, see Fig. 12a. The gaskets for both air permeability and water tightness were easily inserted in the connections, see Fig. 12b. The 3DP lines provided additional gasket support and grip for

Fig. 10. a) Facade panels front surface 1600 mm × 2000 mm assembled on site; b) Gaps and fabrication errors; c) Intersection between the front surface and infill produced minor mistakes in the geometry or material protrusion; d) Infill is not connected in specific areas of the geometry; e) Couplings integrated in the first two layers of the design distanced at 100 mm length.

Fig. 11. a) Infill gradient fabrication and integrated brackets in the back surface of the panel; b) HcA and HcB horizontal connections, and VcA and VcB vertical connections (longer samples).

firmly securing the connections. Therefore, the advantage of 3DP lines secures a better grip compared to conventional solutions.

The gaps between the facade panels, connections, and the facade testing chamber were sealed with silicone, see Fig. 12c. The assembly to the structural wooden beam was tightly secured with metal parts, to which all brackets of the facade panels fitted successfully, see Fig. 12d. As a result, both panels and their corresponding connections were easily integrated into a single facade element, see Fig. 12e. Dismantling was performed and analyzed by the testing specialist after all the performance tests. The facade panels and connections were measured during the dismantling process and compared to the computational model. No deviations from the drawings were found.

3.3. Air permeability

These tests were carried out at a temperature of 22.7 °C and relative humidity of 69 % for both negative and positive test pressures, see Fig. 13. The facade element air permeability was performed before and after the wind load serviceability test.

Table 4 values display an air infiltration larger than 1.5 m³/m²·h permissible Class 1 value, which is 0.5 m³/m²·h, based on the SN

Fig. 12. a) Assembly of HcB with fastener (I) in the facade panel; b) Air permeability gasket being fitted in the connection gap; c) Silicone sealant for the gap occurring at the contact between the front facade panel and outdoor wooden plank; d) Metal brackets as part of the structural system attached to a wooden beam and their fit with the 3DP brackets of the facade panel; e) Back and front surface of the facade panels installed in the test chamber.

EN 13116:2001 standard. These high values are estimated to be caused by print path errors and gaps in specific areas of the panel and connections. Due to these fabrication errors, the test cannot be classified according to the SN EN 12152:2002 standard. The authors recommend that further iterative fabrication tests are performed to overcome such print path gaps. For the panels, a larger than 65° overhang and an increased material extrusion output to 56–58 could contribute to a more accurate outcome. For the connections, a functional gradient of varying print path that considers the robotic acceleration is recommended to prevent gaps in the connections infill.

3.4. Water tightness

The water tightness test was carried out at a temperature of 24.8°C and a relative humidity of 55%. This test was duplicated twice, mirroring the procedure for air permeability tests, conducted both prior to and following the wind loads resistance serviceability test, see Fig. 14a. For the first test, the water was sprayed for 22 min, with water infiltrating after 2 min in Panel 2, see Fig. 14b. Then, the first pressure stage of 50 Pa was applied, which led to some water droplets infiltrating in Panel 1. For the second test, the water was sprayed for 12 min, where after 7 min water flowed substantially in both panels. Therefore, the facade element does not qualify for water tightness. This effect is due to the similar causes in air permeability of gaps occurring in both the facade panels and connections, due to fabrication errors.

3.5. Resistance to wind loads

The resistance to wind loads tests were carried out at a temperature of 24.6°C and a relative humidity of 56%. These tests were carried out in three experimental steps for: (i) serviceability, (ii) safety load, and (iii) breaking load. The panel's serviceability (i) tests were subjected to both positive (wind suction) and negative (wind pressure) loads at 375, 750, 1125, and 1500 Pa. Then, a safety load was applied of 2500 Pa and -2500 Pa after the air permeability and water tightness performance tests. Finally, a breaking load was tested with increasing pressure until the facade element broke or the maximum power of the fan was reached. The absolute values of

Fig. 13. Air permeability to area qA at negative test pressure and positive test pressure.

Table 4
Difference in air permeability measurements.

Test pressure	Air permeability area qA	Air permeability joint qL	Class 1 permissible value qA	Class 1 permissible value qL
-150 Pa	26.62 m ³ /m ² ·h	43.92 m ³ /m·h	≤1.5 m ³ /m ² ·h	≤0.5 m ³ /m·h
150 Pa	25.38 m ³ /m ² ·h	41.87 m ³ /m·h	≤1.5 m ³ /m ² ·h	≤0.5 m ³ /m·h

Fig. 14. a) Test procedure water tightness under static pressure before (picture on the left) and after (picture on the right) the resistance to wind loads tests b) Test setup for with nozzles spraying water at 6.6 l/min. In the second test after the resistance to wind load tests water ingress was visible in Panels 1 and 2.

the deformation sensors measured results can be seen in Table 5.

The first tests of serviceability have good deformation and deflection values. The deformations recovered back to 95 % after 1 min during the tests, which meant that the test could be stopped earlier. Fig. 15 shows the deformation and deflection measurements of the sensors at a) positive test pressure or wind suction and b) negative test pressure or wind pressure. The maximum permissible relative frontal deflection for load-bearing facade elements under wind load serviceability must not be greater than L/200 or 15 mm, according to the SN EN 13116:2001 standard. L was the measured distance between structural points of the frame element or 2000 mm for this facade element. Additionally, the deflection must be temporary and deform back by at least 95 % (or have less than 5 % deformation up to a maximum of 1 hour after loads removal), according to same standard. The tests displayed a less than 5 % deformation with 2.4 % for wind suction and 2.7 % for wind pressure. In this case, the sensor displacements show permanent deformations that should not exceed 1 mm. The displacement was measured by Sensors 1 in the facade panel, with positive deformation of 0.38 mm and negative deformation of 0.3 mm. These values were below the 1 mm sensor displacements for the facade element, which is why it met the required standards according to SN EN 13116:2001 and achieved the -1500 Pa/1500 Pa classification.

The safety load (ii) was carried in the second round of resistance testing at 2250 Pa wind suction and -2250 Pa wind pressure. Fig. 16a displays the applied differential pressures of the design value of the wind load safety. The tested facade element did not break, which meant that no damage to the test specimen was found after the test. Therefore, the facade samples passed the requirements of SN

Table 5
Frontal deflection and recoverability of resistance to wind loads serviceability.

Wind loads (W)	Permissible deformation	Deformation	Recovery deformation	Permanent deformation
Positive loads - wind suction	8.9 mm	0.73 mm	0.02 mm	2.7 %
Negative loads - wind pressure	8.9 mm	0.73 mm	0.015 mm	2.4 %

Fig. 15. a) Positive test pressure or wind suction values of the three sensors for deformation (left diagram) and deflection (right diagram); b) Negative test pressure or wind suction values of the three sensors for deformation (left diagram) and deflection (right diagram).

EN 13116:2001 regarding safety wind loads and achieved the - 2250 Pa/2250 Pa classification.

Finally, a breaking load (iii) was carried after the impact testing. Fig. 16b displays the applied differential pressures. In this test a maximum test pressure of -3262 Pa was achieved with wind pressure, which kept constant at maximum fan power. For wind suction, a maximum test pressure of 2403 Pa was achieved. The pressure could not be maintained afterwards, which indicated a potential break in the facade that resulted in higher air loss through the tested element. Nevertheless, no visual fractures were detected, and the tested facade also remained securely in place within the holder.

To this date, there are no 3DP facade systems tested for resistance to wind loads, to the authors' knowledge. However, when compared to industry benchmarks, these 3DP systems have been validated for real-world architectural applications in Switzerland, specifically in terms of wind load resistance. In general, new facade prototypes, including conventional solutions, may require additional testing and optimization to consistently meet performance standards. This prototype, however, successfully passed the test on the first attempt due to its integration of performance in the computational design.

3.6. Impact resistance

The impact test was applied at the 1000 mm height of the facade panel. During the drop impact height of 200 mm, cracking noises occurred when hitting the facade element. At the drop impact height of 450 mm a 35 mm breach appeared, see Fig. 17. These broken pieces were less than 50 g, and with a gap size smaller than the E2 template, according to SN EN 1630:2021 standard. Therefore, the test could be continued to the maximum drop height of 950 mm, where no additional cracks occurred. Based on these results, the facade element passed the impact test and achieved the E5 classification according to SN EN 14019:2016.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrated how 3DP strategies can build multi-performative geometries in a single-material facade system. A multi-performative thermoplastic prototype was computationally designed, fabricated, and tested for real-world facade applications. The environmental performance results displayed good resistance to wind loads and impact resistance. These values passed the classification of 1500 Pa for serviceability, 2250 Pa for safety load, 3262 Pa for breaking load, and the E5 class maximum impact resistance. Therefore, this facade design was validated for structural strength, according to standards.

However, the air permeability and water tightness required further improvement, due to infiltration in the test chamber during the experiments, caused by the print path gaps of the fabrication process. Due to its complex geometry, both the facade panels and the connections had errors, enabled by the high speed and inconsistent material extrusion which created overhangs and material protrusion. The authors recommend that future investigations perform several iterative fabrication tests with careful consideration of material extrusion values in direct correlation to fabrication speed and robotic acceleration. The geometry requires a consistent and exceptionally accurate print path width. Such investigations can potentially secure that no gaps occur in the large-scale systems and pass the air permeability and water tightness tests. Additionally, identifying suitable 3DP materials for fire protection and resistance is

Fig. 16. a) Application of the safety load wind pressure (left picture) and wind suction (right picture); b) Application of the breaking load wind pressure (left picture) and wind suction (right picture).

Fig. 17. Impact resistance tests with 35 mm breach at impact height drop of 450 mm.

essential for the architectural application of such facade systems.

Nevertheless, the fabrication results displayed no deformations or cracks in the overall panel, which is a common challenge in manufacturing large-scale thermoplastic panels. Additionally, the 3DP connections displayed an efficient method for manufacturing and assembling easy-fit mechanisms. To ensure the experiment's repeatability, the authors recommend the following criteria.

- Optimization of fabrication parameters, such as material extrusion versus robot speed, which varies in the geometry depending on the overhang angle, double curvature, and print path height and width.
- Iterative design and fabrication tests of all individual parts of the facade element, such as connections, infill, and brackets to ensure good fabrication tolerances and mechanical properties.
- Iterative design and fabrication tests of the combined elements in a large-scale panel to secure process repeatability and geometry accuracy.
- Testing the optimized 3D printed facade in a large-scale facade test rig for an accurate assessment in a real-world user case scenario for architectural applications.

While the primary aim of this study focused on the design and physical performance testing of 3DP facade panels, the research also introduces an approach towards circular material use and more sustainable construction practices. The utilization of recycled plastic in

a topological optimized material pattern not only addresses material reuse but also encourages a pathway toward more efficient resource management in architecture. The integration of multiple customizable performances in a single prefabricated system also encourages the potential of passive design strategies. However, the authors acknowledge that further work is needed to comprehensively validate these sustainability claims. Future research will require a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to evaluate the environmental impacts and efficiencies gained through this facade system. Additionally, further exploration of the thermal performance of these panels is necessary to assess their potential for passive design strategies. Investigating the structural capacity and deformation resistance of the panels under varying temperature thresholds will be valuable for understanding the impact of Total Equivalent Temperature Differential (TETD). Such temperature variations may influence structural performance, as well as the air and water permeability of the panels if deformation occurs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ina Cheibas: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ringo Perez Gamote:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Ena Lloret-Fritschi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Kilian Arnold:** Visualization, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Andreas Luible:** Supervision, Resources. **Fabio Gramazio:** Supervision, Resources. **Matthias Kohler:** Supervision, Resources.

Data availability

The data supporting the findings of the paper are available as open access in a Zenodo repository. It contains connection tests, brackets, metallic brackets, and wind load calculations. This document is to support the study claim with additional experiments, drawings, and calculations.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests (e.g., any funding for the research project)/personal relationships (e.g., the author is an employee of a profitable company) which may be considered as potential competing interests.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2024.111251>.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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